

D1.5: Data Management Plan (3)

WP1 – Project Management & Quality assurance

Authors: George Karavias, Stergios Asteriou, George Voutsinos

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Other authors	Stergios Asteriou (KARAVIAS), George Voutsinos (KARAVIAS)		
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Abbreviations

Advisory Board	AB
Agricultural Insurance	AgI
Application Programming Interface	API
Climate Prediction Centre	CPC
Comma Separated Values	CSV
Data Management Plan	DMP
Digital Object Identifier	DOI
Dissemination Exploitation Communication	DEC
Earth Observation	EO
European Commission	EC
Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable	FAIR
Global Forecasting System	GFS
Graph Modeling Language	GML
Horizon 2020	H2020
Landsat-8 Surface Reflectance Level-2	LaSRC
Leaf Area Index	LAI
Letter of Support	LoS
Lighthouse Customers	LHC
Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	NDVI
Open Access	OA
Structured Query Language	SQL
Synthetic Aperture Radar	SAR
Variable Local Analysis and Prediction System	vLAPS
Vegetation Indices	VI
Weather Intelligence Component	WIC
Web Mapping Service	WMS
Work Packages	WP

Executive summary

The present deliverable is a deliverable of the BEACON project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate – General for Research and Innovation, under its Horizon 2020 Innovation Action programme (H2020).

The deliverable presents the third and the final version of the project Data Management Plan (DMP). This version lists the various datasets that have been collected, processed and/ or produced by the BEACON project and outlines the main data sharing and the major management principles that have been followed. Additionally, it incorporated all the critical changes, such as changes in the consortium policies (if any) and any external factors that may had impact on the data management within the project and might influence it, even after the project duration.

The deliverable is structured in the following chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction – Includes an introduction to the deliverable.

Chapter 2: DMP Components in BEACON – Includes a description of the datasets along with the documented changes and additional information.

1. Introduction

The Deliverable D1.5 Data Management Plan (3) represents the third version of the DMP of the BEACON project. BEACON is an Innovation Action project funded under the H2020 program of the EC that lasted 37 months.

This deliverable D1.5 Data Management Plan (3) aims to document all the final updates on the BEACON project data management life cycle for all datasets to have been collected, processed and/ or generated and a description of how the results will be shared, including access procedures and preservation according to the guidelines in Horizon 2020 and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Although, the DMP is being developed by KARAVIAS, its implementation involves all project partners' contribution. Since, this is the final version of the project DMP, all the Work Packages (WP) are included, despite the fact that some of them might have not occurred any changes.

2. DMP Components in BEACON

1.1. DMP Components in WP1 – Project management & Quality assurance (KARAVIAS)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>Contact details of the project partners</p> <p>Databases containing all the necessary information regarding the project partners.</p> <p>The project partners data are stored on a simple table (excel file) and it is stored on the BEACON dropbox folder, with the following fields (per partner):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Name ⊗ Email ⊗ Phone ⊗ Mobile ⊗ Skype id <p>Furthermore, consortium meetings have been conducted remotely every month in order to discuss the project progress and address any important issue. Most meetings have been contacted using Gotomeeting. Minutes have been prepared after each meeting and have been stored on the BEACON dropbox folder (docx. format). Furthermore, recording of each meeting is kept in the same folder (.mp4 format).</p> <p>Plenary meetings have also been conducted remotely, due to the pandemic situation, and the relevant documents have been generated and kept in the respective project dropbox folders.</p> <p>The expected size of the docx. is not applicable. However, the size of each recording is approximately at 95 KB.</p> <p>Moreover, WP leaders have sent input on how they handle the data produced during the project and all the partners provided input with regards to the Risk Management Plan.</p>

	<p>Lastly, the presentations, agenda and the participants list of each plenary or review meeting have been collected and kept.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data with regards to the remote meetings (including the monthly call, the plenary and review meetings) have been stored on KARAVIAS server and in the BEACON dropbox folder. The data are not directly accessible from outside and these data cannot be made available to third parties.</p> <p>However, the input provided with regards to the data and risk management are available in the respective deliverables; D1.3 Data management plan, D1.4 Data management plan (2), D1.5 Data management plan (3), D1.6 Risk management plan, D1.7 Risk management plan (2) and D1.8 Risk management plan (3). The dissemination level of these deliverables is public and they are available in the project’s website (http://beacon-h2020.com/), dropbox folder and in Zenodo¹ (https://zenodo.org/communities/beacon_h2020/) through the Digital Object Identifier (DOI):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ D1.3 Data Management Plan (1): DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3611345 ⊗ D1.4 Data Management Plan (2): DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4662749 ⊗ D1.6 Risk Management Plan (1): DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465497 ⊗ D1.7 Risk Management Plan (2): DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4447235 ⊗ D1.8 Risk Management Plan (3): DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5865549 <p>The naming convention used for these data are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Data_WP1_1_Data Management Plan ⊗ Data_WP1_2_Risk Management Plan <p>As part of any stored data, metadata were generated, which include sufficient information with appropriate keywords to help external and internal users to locate data and related information.</p>

¹ <http://zenodo.org/>

Making data openly accessible	The datasets are not publicly available. All the data have been made publicly available as part of the aforementioned deliverables and through BEACON website, dropbox folder and Zenodo.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	Data are publicly available as part of the aforementioned deliverables and can be accessed and re-used by third parties indefinitely without a license.
Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP1 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	The data have been collected for internal use in the project, and not intended for long-term preservation. No personal information will be kept after the end of the project. Furthermore, KARAVIAS pays special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data by fully complying with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

1.2. DMP Components in WP2 – Structural AgI value chain collaboration and co-evolution of business models and services (UBFCE)

1.2.1. User and technical requirements

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	Questionnaires were designed during the user requirements collection and analysis process. The questionnaires were targeted to companies involved in AgI business, so called BEACON Lighthouse Customers. In addition, with 3 AgI companies (KARAVIAS, Agroseguro and Triglav) teleconference interviews

	<p>were held and recorded. The responses collected both by questionnaires and interviews provided data such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ General information ⊗ Companies’ geographical area of business activity ⊗ Companies’ specific practices and business models ⊗ Companies’ preferences related to BEACON solutions <p>These data were processed by the BEACON technical partners and used to exact the user requirements for the BEACON toolbox functionalities as well as the technical requirements of the BEACON services. Thus, the requirements enabled us to develop user friendly and highly useful solutions for Agri business models.</p> <p>The feedback on the first questionnaire was collected in word document, and second questionnaire was provided to the Agri companies as a Google Form. The answers are download and organized in an excel file (.xlsx) of 12KB.</p> <p>The recorded interviews are stored as MP4 files of 47-75MB.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data have been stored on the UBFCE servers. As it contains confidential and personal data, the raw data have not been made available from outside but anonymized data have been made available upon request and after an evaluation of the request (i.e. purposes, goals. etc.).</p> <p>The naming conventions used are:</p> <p>Data_WP2_1_User requirements</p> <p>Data_WP2_2_Technical requirements</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>The data have been kept closed until the end of the project due to data contain personal data and therefore, it cannot legally be made public.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>Any data published in papers will be immediately available to meta-analysis. However, it is not legal to</p>

	the system upon the stakeholders' opinion and recommendations.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data are stored on the UBFCE servers. As it may contain confidential and personal data, the raw data have not been made available from outside. The naming convention used is: Data_WP2_3_Co-creation
Making data openly accessible	The data have been kept closed until the end of the project due to data contain personal data and therefore it cannot legally be made public.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	Any data published in papers will be immediately available to meta-analysis. However, it is not legal to release personal data such as the questionnaire responses. Raw data contains personal data and cannot legally be made available.
Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP2 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	UBFCE servers have been managed by the university IT services and they are regularly backed up and secure. UBFCE pays special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data by fully complying with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

1.3. DMP Components in WP3 – Servitisation of Agri Business: Creating value by adding Earth Observation data products and services (AgroApps)

2.3.1. Satellite Data Collection, Pre-processing System and EO Data Products

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>In BEACON, different types of EO data have been utilized, processed and “translated” to valuable information for different purposes.</p> <p>One such purpose is the monitoring of parcels throughout piloting phase 1 and piloting phase 2. During pilot phase 1, optical and radar satellite data were collected, preprocessed and visualized for registered parcels in Serbia, Spain and Greece. Multispectral images were employed in both the remote Crop Growth Monitoring module and Damage Assessment Calculator. Radar image data were used to form image stacks that were later used in determining the beginning, extend and duration of an extreme flooding event in Southern Greece. During pilot phase 2, only multispectral satellite data were used for crop growth monitoring and hail damage assessment.</p> <p>Satellite datasets were also acquired and pre-processed for developing, updating and testing different EO products in deliverables <i>D3.6: Operational Data Products Validation Report (1)</i>, <i>D3.7: Operational Data Products Validation Report (2)</i>, <i>D3.8: Operational Data Products Validation Report (3)</i>. The data collected for the validation of EO products, not limited to, but with a main focus on damage assessment calculator, were satellite datasets from both optical and SAR satellite sensors. Optical reflectance imaging data originated from two sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ④ Copernicus Scientific Hub for the acquisition of Sentinel-2 satellite images (https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home); ④ MODIS 8-day NDVI product (https://gimms.gsfc.nasa.gov/MODIS/std/GMOD09Q1/) <p>Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) originated from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ④ Copernicus Scientific Hub for the acquisition of Sentinel-1 radar data (S1 L1 IW GRDH mode) <p>The task produces pre-processed data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ④ Sentinel-2 BOA (GeoTiff format) will be generated using Sen2Cor processor for

atmospheric, terrain and cirrus correction. A number of images were already atmospherically corrected (Sentinel-2 L2A)

- ☉ Sentinel-1 GRD, radiometrically calibrated, terrain corrected (GeoTiff format)
- ☉ MODIS 8-day NDVI Anomaly product

The data were acquired and cropped accordingly to the agricultural parcels' geometry. The insured parcels were registered in BEACON platform. Collected data, regardless of the final purpose that were use, were all stored in the BEACON operational database.

Crop Monitoring Service

After pre-processing, optical satellite data were fed in crop specific models for determining biophysical parameters, among which LAI, chlorophyll content and above ground biomass. Yield estimation was also provided as the product of accumulated biomass and the harvest index. Throughout the growing season, available satellite imagery over the parcels was fully exploited and visualized, through the platform, to the users of BEACON (Karavias, Triglav and AgroSeguro Agl companies). The first and the second piloting phases in all three countries have been completed. The countries were Spain, Serbia and Greece and the crop types were soybean, maize, winter wheat and barley, as well as cotton.

During the pilot phases, data on final received yield were provided by the LHCs Karavias and AgroSeguro. These included wheat and cotton yields. The yields on non-damaged parcels were used to either develop or update the procedures of yield estimation. A new procedure was implemented for automated yield estimation of cotton based on EO data and the determination of the inflection point – End Of Season (EOS) date. A new updated algorithm based on the initial work of Kross et al. (2015) was developed for wheat yield estimation using Sentinel-2 data. Through a similar approach, a crop and region specific algorithm was developed to predict wheat and barley yield for Spain, using as primary data MODIS NDVI datasets and expected yield. The collected provided yields were stored in the BEACON operational database.

Damage Assessment Calculator

EO derived indices and approaches were used to assess crop damage. Damage-specific methodologies have been employed, considering:

- ④ flooded areas detection (mapping and statistics of the flooded and non-flooded area), with the use of optical and radar data; Piloting Phase 1 validation against flooded cotton parcels / Deliverable D3.7 validations against Copernicus EMS events.
- ④ burnt areas detection (mapping, grading and statistics of the affected area from the wildfire), with the use of optical data; Deliverable D3.7 validations against Copernicus EMS events.
- ④ hail and wind damage detection (mapping and statistics of the severity of damage), with optical satellite data; Pre-pilot phase / Piloting phase 2 / Deliverables D3.6 & D3.8 validations against hail damaged parcels.
- ④ crop growth anomaly detection due to drought conditions, based on in-season NDVI deviations from recorded historical data (NDVI Anomaly); Pre-pilot phase / Piloting phase 1 / Deliverables D3.6 & D3.7 validations against drought damaged parcels.

Size of the satellite raw data:

- ④ Sentinel-2 MSI L1C/L2: Raw zipped image per tile size, including all bands, is 600MB;
- ④ Sentinel-1 L1 IW GRDH: Raw zipped image per tile size, including both polarizations and two satellites (S1A, S1B) data, is 1 GB.
- ④ GIMMS MODIS Terra NDVI 9x9 degree Tiles (15 MB per Tile)

Size of the input data:

Considering that the project’s pilot phase last two years and that both winter (wheat and barley) and summer (maize and soybean) crops were monitored, satellite imagery was acquired and processed in different ways for more than 24 months. Based on the satellite, a rough estimation of the data size used for BEACON is:

- ④ Sentinel-2 L2A, BOA: 600 MB x 52 days (considering a mean 7 days revisit period) x 6 tiles

	<p>(pilot areas: Serbia 2 tiles, Greece 2 tiles, Spain 2 tiles), equals to 187.2 GB.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Sentinel-1 CGR: 1 GB x 61 days (considering a mean 6 days revisit period) x 6 tiles, equals to 366 GB. ⊗ MODIS NDVI Anomaly: 2 years x 46 (8-day composites) x 3 Tiles x 15 MB equals to 4.2 GB. NDVI Data used to derive NDVI Anomaly, from 2001, resulted in 6.3 GB of space.
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>INSPIRE metadata have been created for all the EO-based geospatial products that were generated in the lifetime of the project. Metadata stored in the BEACON operational database together with the raster file such as date, bounding box, projection and mission has proven useful for discoverability of the data. The collected imagery was not available for insurers or farmers. The processed data and the derived indices and parameters were available to registered partners and lighthouse customers through map display and reports. In addition, each dataset produced was associated to a unique ID corresponding to the area of interest requested. Naming conventions for the image data were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ S2_BOA_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff (e.g. S2_BOA_AGRO_158_20190808 for the tile requested by the Lighthouse customer Agroseguro and is associated to registered parcel AGRO_158, which was received on 2019/08/08) ⊗ S1_CGR_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff <p>After processing, the produced data have the following names:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ NDVI_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff (e.g. NDVI_AGRO_158_20190808 for the parcel AGRO_158 requested by the Lighthouse customer Agroseguro and was received on 2019/08/08) ⊗ LAI_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff ⊗ BIOMASS_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff ⊗ CHL_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff ⊗ YIELD_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD].tiff

	<p>Change detection derived data have the following names, based on the parcel ID, the date of the extreme weather event and the type of the used index:</p> <p>📡 DAMAGE_NDVI_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD]</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>Only project partners and Lighthouse customers participating in the pilot phase of the project had unlimited access to products related to their registered parcels, for the duration of the project. All the data, associated metadata and documentation were deposited into the official BEACON web server and made available through RESTful API and Geoserver's web mapping service (WMS). Raw satellite data that were used for the development and delivery of the relevant products were not available and accessible to partners and/or LHCs and hence are not open for reuse.</p> <p>Only web browser and Internet access were required to access the data.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>The input and output data are available in GeoTiff or (Graph Modeling Language) GML format with associated metadata and accessible through GeoServer application, Map server application, PostGIS database and RESTful API. INSPIRE protocol has been used for metadata descriptors. INSPIRE provides typical standard for geospatial data.</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>The EO-based products were accessible for use to all BEACON project partners and lighthouse customers participating in the pilot phase through RESTful API from the BEACON database. Raw satellite data that were used for the development and delivery of the relevant products were not available and accessible to partners and/or LHCs and hence are not open for reuse.</p> <p>Appropriate licensing agreement will be required for data access after the project's conclusion, which will be defined through the business model during the course of the project.</p> <p>The EO-based products will be usable by third parties through RESTful API, but only for those parties who are part of the project and during the lifespan of the project.</p>

Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	All the data were stored in the BEACON server for the purpose of servicing data and also on a separate storage server, both with backup procedures. These servers are managed by the AgroApps IT department. AgroApps fully complies with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.3.2. Climate data provision

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p><i>Climate Data provision</i></p> <p>Real-time atmospheric data have been produced by ingesting and assimilating data from surface weather stations and satellite radiances using the variable Local Analysis and Prediction System (vLAPS) and analysis and near to analysis forecasts from the Global Forecasting System (GFS). To enhance the accuracy and the spatial resolution of the minimum and maximum temperature at 2 m height, and of the daily amount of precipitation, the produced gridded atmospheric fields from the vLAPS model have been further processed using a spatio-temporal Kriging regression methodology. These data were used for the verification of extreme weather events that took place in the insured parcels.</p> <p>The high-resolution medium range weather forecasts were based on the operation of the WRF-ARW numerical weather prediction model, using the GFS analysis and forecasts fields of the 12 UTC forecast cycle to define the initial and lateral boundary conditions, accordingly. The produced weather forecasts have a forecast horizon of 7 days, with hourly temporal resolution and a varying spatial resolution</p>

	<p>ranging from 2x2 km for the first 72 hours to 6x6 km from the 73rd forecast hour until the 168th forecast hour.</p> <p>Medium Range forecasting data originates from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the Weather Intelligence Component (WIC), delivered by AGROAPPS team, which is a suite of climate and weather services. The provided services include high resolution short- and medium-range weather forecasts, early warnings for extreme weather events, real-time and historical high-resolution gridded climate data, and they are produced by operating in-house state of the art numerical weather prediction models, combined with advanced data assimilation of open atmospheric and EO-derived land surface observations. The Weather intelligence service package component is offered through a RESTful API. <p>Size of the data:</p> <p>Daily downloaded meteorological data from the Global Numerical Weather Prediction Models, including MADIS observations are approximately 8.4 GB. Daily meteorological products size for near real time weather observations and 7-day forecasting are approximately 12.3 GB.</p> <p>Climatology data for the Weather Risk Probability service of BEACON occupy a standard size of 290 GB and originate from ERA5 historical observations. The ERA5 data are updated yearly with a total of 7.25 GB data covering the European Continent.</p> <p>Generated and collected data were available in the following types and formats:</p> <p>Gridded meteorological data are in .GRIB format and are transformed in .NetCDF file types.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>Metadata such as creation date, version, bounding box, projection, quality of the data will be useful for discoverability of the data. Only registered partners and lighthouse customers were able to visualize meteorological and climatic data for their parcels and</p>

	<p>for a specific date. Along with daily forecast, a log history of extreme weather events was available, as well as warnings for possible pest and diseases occurrence.</p> <p>Naming conventions for the data are in the form:</p> <p>⊗ temp_[ID]_[YYYYMMDD] (e.g. temp_AGRO_158_20190530), that is the temperature requested by Agroseguro lighthouse customer for day 30/05/2019 and for parcel with ID AGRO_158</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>Only project partners and lighthouse customers participating in pilots had permissions to access the data. Clients of the participants also had access to the data, during the pilot phase. All the data, associated metadata and documentation were deposited on official BEACON web server and were available through RESTful API and Geoserver's WMS. Raw data that were used for the development and delivery of the relevant products were not made available and accessible to partners and/or LHCs and hence were not open for reuse.</p> <p>Only web browser and Internet access were needed to access the data.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>The data were in GeoTiff, csv or GML format with associated metadata and provided through RESTful API. Based on that, there is possibility for using in various open software applications.</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>The data were accessible for use to all BEACON project partners and lighthouse customers participating in the pilot phase through RESTful API from the BEACON database. Raw data that were used for the development and delivery of the relevant products were not available and accessible to partners and/or LHCs and hence were not open for reuse.</p> <p>Appropriate licensing agreement will be required for data access after the project's conclusion, which will be defined through the business model during the course of the project.</p>

collected during the two pilot phases in Spain (2020, 2021). For testing and development of the methodologies, non-damaged parcel data were also provided. Apart from the parcel's geospatial data, all cases included crop metadata:

- ⊗ crop type
- ⊗ event causing the damage
- ⊗ date of damage
- ⊗ parcel size
- ⊗ expected yield before the calamity
- ⊗ yield received after the calamity
- ⊗ damage percent
- ⊗ yield received from non-damaged parcels

The following table presents the number of provided damage cases by AgroSeguro during the pre-pilot and pilot cases:

Year	Drought	Hail	Non-Damaged
2014-2015	12	-	-
2015-2016	-	17	117
2016-2017	95	-	53
2017-2018	13	32	-
2018-2019	42	-	-
2019-2020 pilot 1	-	23	109
2020-2021 pilot 2	-	144	35
Total	162	216	314

The Lighthouse customer Agl company Triglav provided a number of in-situ data from wheat, maize and soybean damaging events occurred in Serbia. These pre-pilot events took place during the 2015-2016, 2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019 growing seasons. A number of in-situ damage data were also collected during the two pilot phases (2020, 2021) in Serbia. For testing and development of the methodologies, non-damaged parcel data were also provided. Apart from the parcel's geospatial data, all cases included crop metadata:

- ⊗ crop type
- ⊗ event causing the damage
- ⊗ date of damage
- ⊗ parcel size
- ⊗ expected yield before the calamity

 damage percent

The final received yield was not provided in the case of Serbia. The following table presents the number of provided damage cases by Triglav during the pre-pilot and pilot cases:

Year	Hail		
	wheat	maize	soybean
2015-2016	-	26	22
2016-2017	-	16	11
2017-2018	59	1	24
2018-2019	-	-	-
2019-2020 Pilot 1	33	26	39
2020-2021 Pilot 2	14	18	6
Total	106	87	189

Year	Non-Damaged		
	wheat	maize	soybean
2015-2016	-	-	-
2016-2017	-	-	-
2017-2018	-	-	-
2018-2019	-	55	66
2019-2020 Pilot 1	16	15	7
2020-2021 Pilot 2	146	215	114
Total	162	285	187

During the first pilot phase of BEACON, Karavias Agri Company registered 165 cotton parcels and 84 wheat parcels in the BEACON platform for monitoring of both crop growth and damage, during the growing season of 2019-2020. During the second pilot phase of BEACON, Karavias registered 13 barley parcels and 245 wheat parcels for the growing season 2020-2021.

The above event cases required the acquisition of optical multispectral and SAR imagery. Each EO tile date represented an event and covered a number, if not all, parcel cases.

A rough estimation is that 80 multispectral images (Sentinel 2), with an estimated size of 120 GB, and 80 SAR images (Sentinel 1), with an estimated size of 80 GB, representing the pre- and post-event status of the

	<p>parcels, were acquired for the validation and evaluation of the hail damage assessment EO product.</p> <p>The Drought damage assessment product validation and evaluation required the full acquisition of MODIS NDVI timeseries from 2001 until current dates, with an estimated size of approximately 6.3 GB.</p> <p>For the flood damage assessment, 3 event cases of Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) were used to validate and evaluate the flood extent and delineation. For each event, stacks of S1 SAR images were created (flood and reference stack) in order to capture the flood phenomenon evolution, and to test the change detection tool. This accounted for 147 Sentinel-1 images, of approximately 242 GB of space.</p> <p>For burnt areas detection, grading and crop loss assessment, 3 event cases of CEMS were used to validate and evaluate the wildfires EO product. A total of 20 Sentinel-2 satellite images were acquired, resulting in 21 GB of space.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>Validation data were locally hosted at BEACON server. For each dataset, related metadata described data structure and methodology used to collect and validate the data. Only the technical team had access to these data and they were not used on the BEACON platform.</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP3_1_Validation data.</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>Damage data used for validation purposes was confidential and provided under a confidentiality agreement between AgroApps and the partners or lighthouse customers. All data were locally hosted at the BEACON server.</p> <p>The validation process followed the current state-of-the-art methodologies and the results were presented as reports. Reports were available to the partners.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>The following data formats were produced:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> .xlsx

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📄 .pdf 📍 .shp (raster and vector data) <p>These data files were useful mainly to the BEACON project partners and BEACON Lighthouse Customers for evaluation purposes.</p>
Increase data re-use	The validation reports were available only to the partners of the project.
Allocation of resources	Resources were allocated according to the project plan and WP3 allocated resources. No additional costs were foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	The confidential data (raw data) have been placed in a password area on the BEACON database which is managed by the AgroApps technical team. AgroApps fully complies with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Furthermore, the technical team (AgroApps) has signed three Confidentiality Agreements with the partner UPM and the Lighthouse Customers in order to process and use these data.
Ethical aspects	No data referring to parcels' geospatial information, as well as personal farmers' information has been distributed within the described historical or pilot cases reports.
Other issues	N/A

2.4. DMP Components in WP4 – BEACON toolbox services & functions ecosystem: design and implementation (BEACON toolbox design and implementation) (AgroApps)

2.4.1. System Architecture

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	Functional and non-functional aspects, technical capabilities, components descriptions and dependencies, API descriptions, information flow diagrams, internal and external interfaces, software

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	<p>and hardware requirements and testing procedures related to data specified and validated among the BEACON technical, pilot partners and Lighthouse Customers (LHC).</p> <p>Technical requirement reports have been created in order to describe the aforementioned procedures and requirements for all the pilots.</p> <p>These reports were the basis upon which the system has been developed and will further be modified.</p>
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>The reports have been stored on AgroApps server and are not directly accessible from outside. Moreover, these data are neither available to third parties nor discoverable and accessible to the public, since the level of dissemination of the respective deliverable D4.1 Overall architecture and system design specification is confidential.</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP4_1_System Architecture.</p> <p>No metadata have been produced.</p>
Making data openly accessible	Only the technical team has access to these data.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	N/A
Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	The data have been collected for internal use in the project, and it are not intended to be preserved for long-term. Furthermore, AgroApps fully complies with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.4.2. BEACON Platform

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
<p>Data Summary</p>	<p>Various data, like insured farmers’ personal information, farm information, farm logs, reports and shapefiles containing farm location, integration with third-party application, premiums and thresholds payouts have been generated via the platform. All of these data were useful in order the BEACON services and products to function properly and provide accurate information (such as vegetation indices, damage assessment calculation, weather alerts, payouts notifications).</p> <p>The aforementioned data have been saved in the BEACON central database.</p> <p>All user actions (login, logout, account creation, visits on specific parts of the platform) have been logged and kept in the form of a text file. This log was useful for debugging purposes.</p> <p>Reports containing information on user devices (which browsers and mobile phones) have been useful for marketing and exploitation purposes, as well as decisions regarding the supported browsers and operating systems.</p> <p>Furthermore, damage assessment results alongside with monetary estimation has been generated through the system. These results have been available through the Damage Assessment calculator and have been saved in the BEACON central database. Only the insurers are able to view these results.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data have not been directly accessible from outside. These data are neither available to third parties nor discoverable and accessible to the public, since the level of dissemination of the respective deliverables D4.2 First version of the BEACON toolbox and D4.5 Final version of the BEACON toolbox is confidential.</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP4_2_BEACON platform.</p> <p>Every action on the platform produced meaningful metadata such as time and date of data creation or</p>

	<p>data amendments and owners of actions that took place as well as damage assessment calculations and risk types have been saved along with the inspection results to enhance the discoverability of the results.</p> <p>The database is not discoverable to other network machines operating on the same LAN, VLAN with the DB server or other networks. Therefore, only users with access to the server (BEACON technical team members) are able to discover the database.</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>Only registered users and administrators have access to the data. The data produced by the platform are personal data and have not been shared with others without the user's permission. No open data have been created as part of BEACON.</p> <p>The database is only accessible by the authorized technical team.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>BEACON has been integrated with third-parties' applications (i.e. Geoserbja) in order for the Serbian insurance company to easier retrieve and import the insured parcels into the BEACON system.</p> <p>The raw data are not publicly available.</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	<p>Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.</p>
<p>Data security</p>	<p>All platform generated data have been saved on the BEACON database server. Encryption has been used to protect personal user data like emails and passwords. All data have been transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information.</p> <p>If there was need for updates, the old data have been overwritten and all actions have been audited in detail and a log will be kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. The system was weekly backed up and the backups were kept for 3 days. All backups have been hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.</p>

	<p>All servers have been hosted behind firewalls inspecting all incoming requests against known vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, cookie tampering and cross-site scripting. Finally, IP restriction enforced the secure storage of data.</p> <p>AgroApps pays special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data by fully complying with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Moreover, "Personal Data Protection Policy " and "Terms and Conditions" have been included in the BEACON, in order to inform the users of how BEACON collects, processes, discloses and protects the incoming information.</p> <p>The BEACON platform will not keep personal data and other information after the end of the project.</p>
Ethical aspects	All the generated data have been protected and will not be shared without user's consent.
Other issues	N/A

2.4.3. Blockchain

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>The Blockchain components have not collected data on their own, they only process data which have been collected/ generated in other parts of the BEACON toolchain.</p> <p>The Blockchain component re-uses data from other parts of the BEACON toolchain, especially:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🌐 pesudonymised client data according to GDPR 🌐 parcel/ field data 🌐 contract data 🌐 weather data <p>The exact scope of data to be used depends solely on the supported insurance products which are useful for the insurance companies and their clients.</p>

	In general, only small portions of data have been processed on chain.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Registered users were able to discover the data stored in the Blockchain corresponding to the insurance products and were identifiable via business process identifiers.</p> <p>Meaningful metadata have been produced as a result of every transaction such as transaction hash, block number and timestamp.</p> <p>Clear version numbers were provided via semver (semantic versioning).</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP4_3_Blockchain</p>
Making data openly accessible	<p>The Blockchain component has been run as private, permissioned chain.</p> <p>The data have been stored on blockchain, a distributed ledger. All data were replicated over all participating nodes. For the private, permissioned chain that means that a closed group of validating nodes exist, which mine blocks and validate transactions. Further nodes can enter the network and read the distributed ledger.</p> <p>The Blockchain data are accessed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ in raw form via blockchain nodes ⊗ in readable form via special services and API calls ⊗ optional: via specialized applications which read API and offer a visual representation.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	The data are available for re-use only for the registered users in the BEACON toolbox.
Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	<p>All data have been stored anonymized in the private Blockchain.</p> <p>Etherisc pays special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal</p>

	data by fully complying with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.4.4. Maps produced by the EO and meteorological models

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>One of the main offerings of BEACON is the generation of maps, based on EO and meteorological models and on climatology service, that can help insurers to increase their efficiency.</p> <p>The geolocation metadata, for each type of map produced by each service (monitoring, damage assessment and climatology) have been produced and been depicted in the map as layers.</p>
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Registered insurers were able to discover maps corresponding to the farms of their clients.</p> <p>Meaningful metadata have been produced as a result of every action (time and data of data creation or data amendments, actions that took place, service that produced the map, crop type of depicted farm).</p> <p>The naming convention used was: Data_WP4_4_Maps</p>
Making data openly accessible	<p>Maps that have been produced are not openly accessible. Users must sign in in order to access the produced maps.</p> <p>The maps and the metadata are made available for use by the BEACON applications through the secure API that has been created.</p> <p>The raw data, used for the generation of the maps' layers, that are stored in the BEACON database are only accessible by the authorised technical team.</p>
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	Maps that have been produced during the project are offered to anyone who requests them. After the

	completion of the project, these data will only be available to users who will buy the product.
Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP4 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	<p>All data generated by the platform have been saved on the BEACON server. All data are transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information.</p> <p>In case of necessary updates, the old data are overwritten and all actions are audited in detail and a log is kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. Daily backups for a period of 3 days are kept. All backups are hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.</p> <p>All servers have been hosted behind firewalls inspecting all incoming requests against known vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, cookie tampering and cross-site scripting. Finally, IP restriction enforce the secure storage of data.</p> <p>AgroApps pays special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data by fully complying with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.</p>
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

1.4. DMP Components in WP5 – Creating Business Experience & BEACON Accreditation path (KARAVIAS)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	The purpose of the WP5 data was to identify all needs for pilot implementation, to define the specifications of each pilot case and to perform the pilots testing in an operational environment. Furthermore, the WP5

- ⊗ Final Yield (kg)/ha - the yield that would have been if the insured risk did not happen on the whole parcel
- ⊗ Final Yield (kg)/ha, for non-damaged parcels, either registered or not in the BEACON platform.

Moreover, another table (excel format) with regards to pilot indicators was circulated to the LHCs and containing the following information:

- ⊗ Assumption of administrative and operational costs before BEACON for the selected area (costs of inspections, costs of inspectors)
- ⊗ No of damages that took place
- ⊗ No of inspections performed
- ⊗ No of inspectors deployed
- ⊗ Policies paid (€)
- ⊗ No of Contracts/policies paid
- ⊗ Time of response after a claim
- ⊗ Time needed to organize resources
- ⊗ Time needed to complete the calamity process (including the payment)
- ⊗ % of true claims
- ⊗ % of claims that could be avoided (weather extreme alerts)

Likewise, this table included the sheets with the questions about:

Testing experience:

- ⊗ Importing your contracts' data (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Which method do you use? Is there any additional comment?)
- ⊗ Dashboard (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Is there any additional comment?)
- ⊗ Monitoring (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Is there any additional comment?)
- ⊗ Damage Assessment Tool (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Is there any additional comment?)

- ⊗ Smart Contracts (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Is there any additional comment?)
- ⊗ Store documents (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Is there any additional comment?)
- ⊗ Notifications (How useful is this element to you? Is there any additional comment?)
- ⊗ Climatology (How useful is this element to you? How easy is this element to use? Is there any additional comment?)

Degree of satisfaction:

- ⊗ The BEACON toolbox has an easy access
- ⊗ The BEACON toolbox has an user-friendly interface
- ⊗ The BEACON toolbox has an intuitive navigation
- ⊗ The BEACON toolbox has met our business workflow needs

General:

- ⊗ What are the main Strengths of the BEACON toolbox?
- ⊗ What are the main Weaknesses of the BEACON toolbox?
- ⊗ What are the main Barriers of the BEACON toolbox?
- ⊗ In your opinion, which part of functionality of the BEACON toolbox has the biggest potential for further enhancement?
- ⊗ In your opinion, which part of functionality of the BEACON toolbox do you find the less useful?
- ⊗ Is there any suggestions for future improvements to the BEACON toolbox functionality?

The datasets received from LHCs were stored in a simple table (excel format) along with the Confidentiality Agreement (CA) signed by their side. Both datasets and CAs are kept in the KARAVIAS, AgroApps and InoSens servers.

	<p>InoSens, as pilot execution and training task leader ensured proper execution of the pilots. Therefore, all actors were able to use the provided data and services effectively and were thus able to provide the most relevant and accurate feedback. A set of the training material was designed (pdf file format) and a number of trainings were provided to LHCs in different stages. The Excel was chosen as a main tool for the pilot monitoring and monitoring of the parcels in order to test the accuracy of the BEACON services and accordingly store the results from the testing. Moreover, Trello is serving as a tool for the collection of feedback from the potential end-users to ensure timely reaction on any failures in the pilot approach and in the solution. Most of the trainings were conducted remotely either using Skype or Zoom.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The raw data collected in WP5 were not made publicly available. Not even the results derived from these data process were made publicly available since the dissemination level of the respective deliverables (D5.3 Pilot data validation report and D5.4 Validation report) was confidential.</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP5_1_Evaluation data.</p> <p>The pilot partners and the LHCs were provided with training material in order to better facilitate the pilot implementation phase. This material was requested to be translated into every pilot country's language. The D5.2 BEACON training material was openly accessible through Zenodo:</p> <p> D5.2: BEACON training material: DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4447222</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP5_2_Training material. Data_WP5_3_Validation data No metadata have been or will be generated</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>All raw data collected in WP5 were available for internal use within the project consortium and especially for the validation of the BEACON services.</p>

	The databases were not publicly available. The data are stored on KARAVIAS, InoSens and AgroApps servers.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	The data that have been collected and processed during this WP have been used exclusively for analytical and statistical purposes and will not be re-used.
Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP5 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	The data were collected for internal use in the project and were not intended for long-term preservation. The data have been stored on KARAVIAS, InoSens and AgroApps servers. All companies fully comply with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.
Ethical aspects	CA document has been prepared specifying the main purpose of the data collected and/ or generated within WP5, i.e., these data will be neither available to third parties nor discoverable and accessible to the public, since the parties disclosed to each other information and documentation, which is proprietary and confidential or otherwise generally not available to the public.
Other issues	N/A

1.5. DMP Components in WP6 – BEACON Commercialisation Playbook and Growth Hacking (INOSENS)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	The purpose of data collection in WP6 is to support commercialization of the BEACON toolbox, to define the business models for sustainable growth and to attract attention of global Agricultural Insurance (AgI) players engaging them in the BEACON development.

The data that have been collected and/ or generated within WP6 are representing the mix of the foreground knowledge derived from the experience in project implementation together with new knowledge. In majority, such data are intangible by nature and brings the following results of the project such as: business modeling information, know-how, network of partners, etc.

All findings, derived knowledge, experience from the project implementation as well as expanded network of partners will be used in future business ventures.

Beside WP leader (InoSens), all partners have contributed the data input with regards to reaching of the critical KPIs for growth hacking activities as well as for the creation of BEACON Business Plan. This dataset includes the following details and date related:

- ⊗ Market analysis
- ⊗ Competitive analysis
- ⊗ Business proposition
- ⊗ Service value chain
- ⊗ Identification of economic and non-economic risks
- ⊗ BEACON Business canvas
- ⊗ Roadmap for service implementation and exploitation
- ⊗ Marketing, dissemination and exploitation
- ⊗ Call (date)
- ⊗ Status (LHC, Pending, Not interested)
- ⊗ Result/ Comment

Furthermore, interviews and B2B meetings have been conducted with LHCs in order to inform them about the project status & progress, to explore their involvement and contribution into the project as well as during the business training sessions. Interviews are mostly conducted remotely either using Skype or Zoom (due to a COVID-19 pandemic, only several are conducted in face-to face manner).

The expected size of the data is not applicable here, as the size is not a meaningful measure for the respective WP6 activities (B2B meetings, interviews, market outreach activities, etc.)

	<p>Data can be utilized in future business ventures through applied experience.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data with regards to the interviews with the LHC and the LoS data have been stored on AgroApps server and are not directly accessible from outside. Moreover, these data are neither available to third parties nor discoverable and accessible to the public, since the level of dissemination of the respective deliverables D6.8 Lighthouse Customers Group, D6.9 Lighthouse Customers Group (2) and D6.10 Lighthouse Customers Group (3) is confidential.</p> <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP6_1_LHC</p> <p>Regarding the input provided for the Business Plan and Market Analysis as well as for the growth hacking activities, these data are neither available to third parties nor discoverable and accessible to the public, since the level of dissemination of the respective deliverables (D6.2, D6.3 and D6.4 Report of Growth hacking activities and D6.11, D6.12 and D6.13 Business models and go-to-market strategy) is confidential. Some business modeling and market analysis findings are stored in InoSens server, still not directly accessible from outside.</p> <p>The naming conventions used are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☒ Data_WP6_2_Growth hacking activities ☒ Data_WP6_3_Business Plan ☒ Data_WP6_4_Market Analysis <p>No metadata have been generated.</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>The datasets are not be publicly available. Only the partners have access to the data through the dropbox folder.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Allocation of resources</p>	<p>Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP6 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making these datasets FAIR.</p>

Data security	<p>All the data are saved on the InoSens (WP leader) and AgroApps servers.</p> <p>InoSens and AgroApps pay special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data by fully complying with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.</p>
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	<p>InoSens applies ISO 9001 standard within the organization structure of the company, which acquires the data management procedures for improvement of data quality across data collection system. From the national regulations, InoSens will follow the rules of Law on data security – Republic of Serbia.</p>

1.6. DMP Components in WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion of BEACON (ETAM)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>The aim of the data collected and/ or generated within WP7 is to develop and implement an effective dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy as well as to attract and engage as many AgI enablers as possible, establishing an interactive Advisory Board (AB).</p> <p>The AB members data is described by the following fields (in excel format):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🌐 Name 🌐 Description 🌐 Affiliation 🌐 Organisation 🌐 Country 🌐 Proposed by <p>Interviews have been conducted with the AB members and webinars have been held in order to inform them about the project status and progress. Most interviews</p>

	<p>and webinars have been conducted remotely either using Skype or Gotomeeting.</p> <p>The expected size of the data is not applicable, as the size is not a meaningful measure. Up to now, 4 interviews have been held.</p> <p>Furthermore, all the partners provide reports with regards to the dissemination activities they have performed.</p> <p>Personal data of newsletter subscribers have been collected, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Email address ⊗ First name ⊗ Last name ⊗ Organisation ⊗ Country <p>Personal data of the BEACON website users requesting for further information through the Contact Form, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Name ⊗ Email ⊗ Subject ⊗ Message <p>Regarding direct engagement activities, personal data of stakeholders have been collected in order to personally invite them to support the project. These data are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Email address ⊗ First name ⊗ Last name <p>With respect to the communication of the project’s press releases, for printed and online media, their email addresses are stored.</p> <p>Lastly, for the engagement polls an email address was requested before enabling participation.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The data with regards to the interviews of the AB and the contact details have been stored on ETAM server and are not directly accessible from outside. Moreover, these data cannot be made available to third parties. However, the interviews are available in</p>

D7.4 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report, D7.5 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report (2), D7.6 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report (3) and D7.7 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report (4). The dissemination level of these deliverables is public and they are available in the project’s website and in Zenodo through the DOI:

- ④ D7.4 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3339150>
- ④ D7.5 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report (2): DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4447269>
- ④ D7.6 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report (3): DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4475915>
- ④ D7.7 “Agricultural Ins. Enablers” – Advisory Board report (4): DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5925564>

The naming convention used are:
Data_WP7_1_Advisory Board

Data_WP7_2_Lighthouse Customers

Regarding the input for the dissemination activities, the data have also been stored on ETAM servers and are not directly accessible from outside. These data have been presented in the respective deliverables (D7.2, D7.3 BEACON promotional activities and engagement report), which are publicly available either through the project website or through Zenodo:

- ④ D7.2 BEACON promotional activities and engagement report (1): DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4447249>
- ④ D7.3 BEACON promotional activities and engagement report (2): DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5925180>

The naming convention used is:
Data_WP7_3_Promotional and engagement activities

The general approach regarding the DEC activities and plan was presented in the respective deliverable D7.1

	<p>Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication as well as the D7.2 BEACON promotion activities and engagement report (1) and is accessible through the BEACON website and Zenodo with the following DOI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ D7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication: DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3339140 ⊗ D7.2 BEACON promotion activities and engagement report (1): DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4447249 <p>The naming convention used is: Data_WP7_4_DEC</p> <p>As part of any stored data, metadata have been and will be generated, which include sufficient information with appropriate keywords to help external and internal users to locate data and related information.</p> <p>With regards to the newsletter subscribers, the data have been stored in the BEACON website database and are not directly accessible from outside. These data have not been presented in any report or deliverable but an indicator (the sum of the subscribers) has been presented in the respective reports. The same approach has been followed with the data collected from the Contact Form.</p> <p>The name conventions used are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Data_WP7_5_Newsletter subscribers ⊗ Data_WP7_6_Contact form <p>No metadata have been generated.</p>
Making data openly accessible	<p>The datasets are not publicly available.</p> <p>All the data have been made publicly available as part of the aforementioned deliverables and can be accessed and re-used by third parties indefinitely without any restrictions.</p>
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	<p>Data are publicly available as part of the aforementioned deliverables and can be accessed and re-used by third parties indefinitely without any restrictions.</p>

D1.5 Data Management Plan (3)

Allocation of resources	Resources have been allocated according to the project plan and WP7 allocated resources. No additional costs are foreseen for making this dataset FAIR.
Data security	<p>All data collected data have been saved on BEACON website database.</p> <p>The personal data collected and/ or generated throughout the project's lifetime will not be kept after the end of the project.</p> <p>ETAM fully complies with the applicable national, European and international framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Moreover, "Privacy Policy" and "Terms and Conditions" have been included in the BEACON website, in order to inform the users of how BEACON collects, processes, discloses and protects the incoming information.</p>
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

